

FRACTURE MECHANISM AND STRENGTH PREDICTION OF IN-SITU TiB₂/AL COMPOSITEMin-ge. Duan¹, Jie Su² and Yazhi. Li³¹ School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China, hopeflydream@mail.nwpu.edu.cn² School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China, yysj0802@163.com³ School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China, yazhi.li@nwpu.edu.cn and <http://teacher.nwpu.edu.cn/liyazhi.html>**Keywords:** In-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite, Ductile-brittle fracture, Mori-Tanaka homogenization technique, Statistical damage model, Porous metal plasticity model**ABSTRACT**

In order to reveal the deformation, damage and fracture behavior of in-situ TiB₂ particle reinforced 2024 aluminum matrix composite prepared by mixed salt reaction method, a ductile-brittle damage constitutive model is proposed according to the constitutive relations of every constituents and their fracture characteristics. Mori-Tanaka homogenization technique was adopted to describe stress and strain distributions among the TiB₂ particles and the Al matrix. It is assumed that the particles are isotropic, linear elastic and brittle in nature and the maximum principal stress failure criterion applies. The composite matrix is assumed isotropic hardened and follows the Ludwik power law, and Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman (GTN) model is used to describe its plastic potential as well as the micro void nucleation, growth and coalescence. To quantify the influence of particle fracture on the ductile fracture of the matrix, the particle strength is considered subject to Weibull distribution, and the broken particles are regarded as the nucleation of the micro voids in the homogenization method. The particle failure probability was then taken as the proportions of the particle volume fraction reduction. The proposed ductile-brittle damage model is calibrated and validated by the uniaxial tension response and fracture behaviour of a smooth round bar and the notched round bars with different notch radii. The simulation results indicate that the model proposed is capable of predicting the deformation and damage behavior of in-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite in complex stress states.

1 INTRODUCTION

Particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) have attracted extensive attention and research effort for their higher specific strength, fatigue resistance and wear resistance than the corresponding parent metals.

However, the micro-structure and damage-fracture mechanism of PRAMCs are more complex than those of their parent metals. The damage mechanism during fracture needs to be fully explored and described with appropriate constitutive model to characterize the deformation, damage and fracture process, so as to promote their application in engineering structures.

Traditional PRAMCs, abbreviated to ex-PRAMCs, are usually fabricated by externally adding particles into metal with physical methods such as powder metallurgy and liquid stirring casting. In-situ PRAMCs are usually fabricated by precipitating in-situ particles from molten metal via chemical reaction, such as the mixed salt reaction method. In-situ PRAMCs are of much smaller and regular particles and stronger particle-matrix interface than those of the ex-PRAMCs. Fig.1 shows the microstructure of both ex-PRAMCs and in-situ PRAMCs. The particles of in-situ PRAMCs are much smaller than those in ex-PRAMCs. The particles of in-situ PRAMCs can be grouped as sparsely distributed nano particles (dispersed nano-particle) inner grains of the matrix and segregated distributed sub-micro particles near the grain boundary of the matrix. Some of the particles in particle segregation zone congregate to form the particle clusters.

Fig. 1 The microstructure obtained by SEM: (a) Ex-PRAMCs; (b) Reticular structure of in-situ PRAMCs; (c) The dispersed nano-particle in matrix and particle cluster in particle segregation of in-situ PRAMCs.

Previous researches have focused on the particle strengthen effects with experimental techniques, which have revealed that the Young's modulus, yield stress and tensile fracture stress of ex-PRAMCs are improved due to the direct strengthen mechanism, i.e. the load transfer mechanism. The mechanical properties and fracture process of PRAMCs are seriously affected by the elastic-plastic fracture behavior of matrix, the strength of the particles and particle-matrix interface, so the damage modes of PRAMCs could be the particle cracking, particle-matrix interface debonding and the ductile failure of the matrix. Generally, three damage modes coexist and one or two of them dominant¹. The strengthen effect and fracture behavior of the PRAMCs are seriously influenced by the content, size, shape and distribution of the particles.²⁻⁶

Previous studies on the in-situ PRAMCs indicate that the Young's modulus are improved due to the direct strengthen mechanism, while the improvement of yield strength and ultimate strength are attributed to both direct and indirect strengthen mechanisms, such as dislocation strengthening from the dispersed nano-particles and the load strengthening from the segregated particles. The Young's modulus of the matrix is almost the same as that of the parent metal. However, the strength characteristics of the matrix is evidently higher than its parent metal. The fracture of the in-situ PRAMCs consists of the particle cluster brittle fracture and matrix ductile fracture.⁷⁻¹¹

In this paper, the TiB₂ particle reinforced 2024 aluminum alloy with a volume fraction of 5% prepared by mixed salt reaction method (briefly as in-situ TiB₂/2024Al) were studied. A ductile-brittle damage model is proposed according to the constitutive relations of every constituents and their fracture characteristics. The proposed model is used to analyse the fracture process of notched round bars with different notch radii, in order to show the capability of the model to characterize the strength behaviour of the in-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite in complex stress states.

2 DUCTILE-BRITTLE CONSTITUTIVE MODELS

The fracture of particles is closely related to the maximum principal stress and particle size. The aluminum alloy matrix is the ductile metal and undergoes void nucleation, growth and aggregation before final failure. Furthermore, it was found in the in situ tensile test of TiB₂/2024 composites by SEM that⁷: 1) the local plastic deformation of the matrix near the crack tip results in the crack tip of the fractured particles blunting; 2) at the later stage of deformation, local necking bands occur in the matrix with sparse particles; 3) in the fractography analysis, a large number of dimples without TiB₂ particles can be observed in the matrix. These phenomena indicate that the matrix region exhibits typical ductile damage characteristics, so the micro-void mesoscopic theory, porous metal plasticity model, can be used to quantitatively describe its damage behavior. Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman (GTN) model is used to describe its plastic potential as well as the micro voids nucleation, growth and coalescence.

The maximum principle stress criterion was used to determine the particle failure probability, which was then taken as the proportions of the particle volume fraction reduction. It is assumed that the composite matrix is isotropic hardened and follows the Ludwik power law, and. To quantify the influence of particle fracture on the ductile fracture of the matrix, the cracked particles are regarded as the nucleation of the micro voids in the homogenization method.

The GTN model, Weibull probability distribution model and Mori-Tanaka homogenization method are briefly introduced in the following sub-sections.

2.1 GTN Model

GTN model can describe the whole damage evolution process during ductile fracture from void initiation to final fracture under tensile loading, for which the evolving yield surface is written as¹²⁻¹⁵:

$$\Phi = \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{eq}}}{\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}} \right)^2 + 2q_1 f^* \cosh \left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_{\text{H}}}{2\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}} \right) - (1 + q_1^2 f^{*2}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where, σ_{H} and σ_{eq} are the hydrostatic stress and the von Mises stress; f^* is the nominal void volume fraction and is a function of void volume fraction f ; q_1 and q_2 are the material constants; $\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}} = \bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}(\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}})$ is the flow stress of the matrix without voids, which is a function of equivalent plastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}}$.

$$\sigma_{\text{H}} = \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{ij} \delta_{ij}, \quad \sigma_{\text{eq}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} s_{ij} s_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

$$f^* = \begin{cases} f, & f < f_c \\ f_c + \frac{1/q_1 - f_c}{f_f - f_c} (f - f_c), & f_c \leq f < f_f \\ 1/q_1, & f \geq f_f \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where, f_c is the critical void volume fraction at the beginning of void coalescence; f_f is the void volume fraction at material failure.

$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}}$ can be determined by conservation of plastic work:

$$(1 - f) \bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}} d\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}} = \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{p}} \quad (4)$$

where, σ_{ij} and $d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{p}}$ are components of the stresses and the plastic strain increment in macro scale.

The evolution of void volume fraction df is divided into nucleation and growth components⁵, $df_{\text{nucleation}}$ and df_{growth} .

$$df = df_{\text{growth}} + df_{\text{nucleation}} \quad (5-a)$$

Due to plastic incompressibility, the void growth rate is written as:

$$df_{\text{growth}} = (1 - f) d\varepsilon_{kk}^{\text{p}} \quad (5-b)$$

Void nucleation is assumed to be plastic controlled as suggested by Needleman¹⁶, which can be expressed as:

$$df_{\text{nucleation}} = A d\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}} \quad (5-c)$$

where, $d\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}}$ is the equivalent plastic strain increment of matrix without voids; A is the void nucleation intensity, which obey Gaussian distribution and can be expressed as:

$$A = \frac{f_N}{s_N \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}} - \varepsilon_N}{s_N} \right)^2 \right] \quad (d\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{m}}^{\text{p}} > 0) \quad (6)$$

where f_N is the critical void volume fraction of void nucleation; ε_N is the mean equivalent plastic strain of void nucleation; s_N is the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution

2.2 Weibull Probability Model

It is assumed that there are many micro cracks in brittle materials, which do not interfere with each other. Fracture begins at the weakest point. Weibull probability model^{17,18} can be used to determine the fracture probability (P_f) of brittle material with given volume (V), aspect ratio (α) and strain (ε).

$$P_f(\alpha, \varepsilon, V) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -\frac{V}{V_0} \left[\frac{\sigma_p(\alpha, \varepsilon, V)}{S_0} \right]^m \right\} \quad (7)$$

where, S_0 and m is the scale and shape parameters of the model. The scale parameter in the brittle cracking problem can be termed as characteristic strength. V_0 is the corresponding volume of brittle media subjected to stress $\sigma_p = S_0$ with a fracture probability of 63.21%.

With the assumption that the particles in the in-situ TiB₂/2024 are in the same volume of V_0 , the maximum principle stress criterion is accepted for particle fracture, and σ_p in Eq.(7) is the maximum principle stress in the particles, the fracture probability of a particle can be simplified as:

$$P_f(\sigma_1) = 1 - \exp \left[-\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (8)$$

2.3 Mori-Tanaka Homogenization Technique

Equivalent methodology is widely used to predict the mechanical properties of composites at macroscopic level from the mechanical properties of its constituents in microscopic level, such as Eshelby equivalent inclusion theory¹⁹, the sparse solution²⁰, self-consistent method²¹⁻²³, generalized self-consistent method²⁴ and Mori-Tanaka method^{25,26}. Mori-Tanaka method is adopted because of its clear physical meaning, simplicity of analysis, and able to consider the interaction between inclusion and the matrix.

When a single ellipsoidal inclusion embedded in an infinite matrix and subjected to a remote uniform strain ε_{ij}^r , the strain of the inclusion ε_{ij}^p can be expressed as¹⁹:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^p = A_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{kl}^r = \left\{ I_{ijkl} + S_{ijmn} \left[\left(C_{mnop}^{\tan,m} \right)^{-1} C_{opkl}^{\tan,p} - I_{mnkl} \right] \right\}^{-1} \varepsilon_{kl}^r \quad (9)$$

where A_{ijkl} is the strain concentration tensor of the inclusion, I_{ijkl} is the fourth-order symmetric identity tensor; S_{ijkl} is the Eshelby's tensor, $C_{ijkl}^{\tan,m}$ and $C_{ijkl}^{\tan,p}$ are the elasto-plastic tangent operators of matrix and inclusion separately.

In in-situ TiB₂/2024Al, a quite large number of particles segregates near the grain boundary of Al matrix, which results in non-negligible interaction between particles. Therefore, in Mori-Tanaka method the remote uniform strain ε_{ij}^r is replaced by the matrix mean strain $\langle \varepsilon_{kl}^m \rangle$, and the increment of the particle strain can be expressed as:

$$d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle = A_{ijkl} d\langle \varepsilon_{kl}^m \rangle \quad (10)$$

where, $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle$ and $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^m \rangle$ are the increment of $\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle$ and $\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^m \rangle$, respectively.

The increments of the mean stress and strain, $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle$ and $d\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$, are dependent on the increments of mean stresses and strains of particle and the matrix, and can be expressed as:

$$d\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle = f^p d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle + (1 - f^p) d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^m \rangle, \quad d\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = f^p d\langle \sigma_{ij}^p \rangle + (1 - f^p) d\langle \sigma_{ij}^m \rangle \quad (11)$$

where, f^p is the particle volume fraction.

Combining Eqs.(10) and (11), $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^m \rangle$, $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle$ and $d\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle$ can be expressed as:

$$d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^m \rangle = \left[f^p A_{ijkl} + (1 - f^p) I_{ijkl} \right]^{-1} d\langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle \quad (12)$$

$$d\langle \varepsilon_{ij}^p \rangle = A_{ijkl} \left[f^p A_{ijkl} + (1 - f^p) I_{ijkl} \right]^{-1} d\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle \quad (13)$$

$$d\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = f^p C_{ijkl}^{\tan,p} d\langle \varepsilon_{kl}^p \rangle + (1 - f^p) C_{ijkl}^{\tan,m} d\langle \varepsilon_{kl}^m \rangle \quad (14)$$

It is noted that for given mean strain increment $d\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle$, the strain concentration tensor of the inclusion A_{ijkl} is the key for determining the mean strain increments of the particle and matrix. The elasto-plastic tangent operators of the matrix and inclusion, $C_{ijkl}^{\tan,m}$ and $C_{ijkl}^{\tan,p}$, as well as the Eshelby's

tensor S_{ijkl} , are needed to determine the strain concentration tensor of the inclusion A_{ijkl} .

2.3.1 The tangent operators

The particle is linear elastic before cracking, the tangent operator $C_{ijkl}^{\text{tan,p}}$ is actually its Hooke's elastic tensor.

The strain increment of the matrix $d\varepsilon_{kl}$ consists of the elastic part $d\varepsilon_{kl}^e$ and plastic part $d\varepsilon_{kl}^p$. The increment of stress $d\sigma_{ij}$ can be expressed as:

$$d\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^m d\varepsilon_{kl}^e = C_{ijkl}^m (d\varepsilon_{kl} - d\varepsilon_{kl}^p), \quad d\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^{\text{tan,m}} d\varepsilon_{kl} \quad (16)$$

where, $C_{ijkl}^{\text{tan,m}}$ is the tangent operators of the matrix, C_{ijkl}^m is the fourth order Hooke elastic tensor and can be expressed as:

$$C_{ijkl}^m = 3K \left(\frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} \right) + 2G \left[\frac{1}{2} (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}) - \frac{1}{3} \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} \right] \quad (17)$$

where, K is the volume modulus, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker's symbol, G is the shear modulus.

The tangent operators for the Mises plasticity model can be expressed as:

$$C_{ijkl}^{\text{tan,m}} = C_{ijkl}^m - \frac{9G^2 S_{ij} S_{kl}}{\sigma_{\text{eq}}^2 [3G + kn(\varepsilon^p)^{n-1}]} \quad (18)$$

The tangent operators for GTN model can be expressed as:

$$C_{ijkl}^{\text{tan,m}} = C_{ijkl}^m - \frac{C_{ijmn}^m \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{mn}} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{op}} C_{opkl}^m}{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{ab}} C_{abcd}^m \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{cd}} - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}_m^p} d\bar{\varepsilon}_m^p - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial f} df} \quad (19)$$

2.3.2 Eshelby Tensor

If the matrix is isotropic and the particle is spherical, the Eshelby tensor S_{ijkl} is only dependent on the tangent Poisson ratio ν^t :

$$S_{ijkl} = \frac{5\nu^t - 1}{15(1 - \nu^t)} \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \frac{4 - 5\nu^t}{15(1 - \nu^t)} (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}) \quad (20)$$

$$\nu^t = \frac{3K^t - 2G^t}{2(3K^t + G^t)} \quad (21)$$

where, K^t is the tangent volume modulus, G^t is the tangent shear modulus. If the matrix is linear elastic, the tangent Poisson ratio reduces to Poisson's ratio.

When there is plastic deformation, the tangent volume modulus K^t and the tangent shear modulus G^t for GTN model are expressed as:

$$K^t = K - \frac{9 \left[\frac{Kq_1 q_2 f^*}{\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}} \sinh\left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_{\text{H}}}{2\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}}\right) \right]^2}{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{ab}} C_{abcd}^m \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{cd}} - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}_m^p} d\bar{\varepsilon}_m^p - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial f} df} \quad (22)$$

$$G^t = G - \frac{2.4 \left[\frac{G\sigma_{\text{eq}}}{(\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}})^2} \right]^2}{\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{ab}} C_{abcd}^m \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{cd}} - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}_m^p} d\bar{\varepsilon}_m^p - \frac{1}{d\lambda} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial f} df} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} = \frac{2\sigma_{\text{eq}}}{(\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}})^2} \frac{3s_{ij}}{2\sigma_{\text{eq}}} + \frac{q_1 q_2 f^* \delta_{ij}}{\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}} \sinh\left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_{\text{H}}}{2\bar{\sigma}_{\text{mf}}}\right) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \bar{\varepsilon}_m^p} = - \left\{ \frac{2\sigma_{eq}^2}{\bar{\sigma}_{mf}^3} + \frac{3q_1 q_2 f^* \sigma_H}{\bar{\sigma}_{mf}^2} \sinh \left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_H}{2\bar{\sigma}_{mf}} \right) \right\} \left(\frac{d\bar{\sigma}_{mf}}{d\bar{\varepsilon}_m^p} \right) \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial f} = \left[2q_1 \cosh \left(\frac{3q_2 \sigma_H}{2\bar{\sigma}_{mf}} \right) - 2q_1^2 f^* \right] \left(\frac{1/q_1 - f_c}{f_f - f_c} \right) \quad (26)$$

2.4 Ductile-brittle constitutive model

In PRAMCs, the particle cracking enhances the plastic deformation and ductile damage of the matrix and contributes to the mechanical properties degradation of the composites. Therefore, the influence of particles breaking should be taken into consideration, during the Mori-Tanaka homogenization analysis to define the constitutive relationship between composites and their constituents.

In in-situ TiB₂/2024Al, the particles cracking leads to large plastic deformation of the matrix in the vicinity of the crack tips, which should be responsible to the further void nucleation. Thus, the volume fraction increment df_p induced by the particle fracture is converted into the increment of particle volume fraction:

$$df_{\text{nucleation}} = df_p = \begin{cases} f_{pt} - [1 - P_f(\sigma_1)] f_{p0} & , f_{pt} > [1 - P_f(\sigma_1)] f_{p0} \\ 0 & , f_{pt} \leq [1 - P_f(\sigma_1)] f_{p0} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where, f_{p0} is the initial particle volume fraction, f_{pt} is the latest particle volume fraction.

To sum up, in the multi-scale ductile-brittle damage constitutive model proposed for the in-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite, the Mori-Tanaka method presents a stress and strain distribution between particles and the matrix at the macro-scale. On the other hand, the model comprises a linear brittle cracking model described by Weibull distribution for particles and a porous plastic damage model namely the GTN model for matrix. The particle fracture is directly related to the void nucleation.

3 COUPON TEST AND SIMULATION

3.1 Experiments

The uniaxial tension tests of the standard smooth round bar (SRB) specimens and notched round bar (NRB) specimens were carried out on an electronic testing machine. Fig.1 shows the geometry of the notched round bar specimens with the notch radii of 4mm and 8mm respectively. There are two types of the materials for the specimens, in-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite and 2024 aluminum alloy, all with the T4 treatment.

The loading rate is 1mm/min. The gauge length of the extensometer used for notched round bars are 25mm. Fig. 1 (b) and (c) illustrate a specimen ready for testing and after fracture respectively.

Fig. 1 The uniaxial tension test of notched round bars: (a) the specimen geometry; (b) specimen ready for testing; (c) fractured specimen after testing.

3.2 Numerical study

The axisymmetric finite element models for SRB and NRB specimens are established, as shown in Fig. 2. The element type is CAX4R. The meshes are refined near the central section of the models.

Fig. 2 Finite element model: (a) smooth round bar; (b) notched round bar with notch radius of 4mm; (c) notched round bar with notch radius of 8mm.

The material parameters used in the ductile-brittle constitutive relation of the in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/2024\text{Al}$ composite are listed in Table 1. Our research group has obtained the basic mechanical properties by experiments, the yield stress and the hardening exponent by an inverse method with nano-indentation experiment, which is detailed described by Su^{11,27}. The Weibull shape parameter m for particles is determined by trial and error to have the simulated stress-strain curve of the SRB model approach the test curve of the SRB specimen, which we can see in Fig. 3. The critical void volume fraction f_c is obtained by trial and error to have the simulated tensile force-deformation curve of the NRB with 4mm notch approach the measured curve, as seen in Fig. 4, where the tensile deformation of the extensometer is used.

Table 1 The material properties for ductile-brittle model

Particle	E(GPa)	ν	$S_0(\text{MPa})$	m	$f_p(\%)$					
	565 ²⁸	0.108 ²⁸	1000 ^{28,29}	20	5.0					
Matrix	E(GPa)	ν	$\sigma_0(\text{MPa})$	$k(\text{MPa})$	n	$f_t(\%)$	$f_0(\%)$	$f_c(\%)$	q_1	q_2
	68.91 ^{11,27}	0.33 ²⁷	299.1	734.26 ²⁷	0.4245 ²⁷	15.8 ¹³	0.4 ¹³	6.8	1.5 ^{14,15}	1.0 ^{14,15}

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curve of SRB

Fig. 4 Force-deformation curve of NRB-R4

Fig. 5 Force-deformation curve of NRB-R8

The proposed ductile-brittle damage constitutive model is validated for NRB specimens with notch radius 8mm. The simulated tensile force-deformation curve correlates well with measured curves, indicating that the proposed model can reasonably characterize the mechanical behaviour of in-situ TiB₂/2024Al composite subjected to complex load and stress state.

4 RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The evolution of particle breaking in terms of particles volume fraction v_p , the micro-void growth δv_{fm} and the volume fraction of voids v_f , are discussed in the following sub-sections.

4.1 The evolution of particle volume fraction

Fig.6 shows the contours of particle volume fraction of NRB specimens at tensile deformation $U_2=0.066\text{mm}$, which reveals that the smaller the notch radius, the more frequent the particle fracture occurs and the faster the particle volume reduces.

Fig.6 Contours of particle volume fraction at $U_2=0.066\text{mm}$

For points C and E of the smallest cross section (Fig. 6), locating at center point and notch root respectively, the variation of particle volume fraction, the particle maximum principle stress as well as the matrix equivalent plastic strain are drawn in Figs. 7 and 8 separately.

For the NRB with notch radius R4, the particles volume fraction at the edge point E is always lower than that of the central point C, which results from the observation that particle maximum principle stress at point E is always larger than that at point C when the tensile elongation is smaller than 0.06mm. Beyond this stage of deformation, the particles volume fraction at point E has already reduced to zero. The increase of the equivalent plastic strain in matrix is closely related to the increase of particle principal stress and the reduction of particle volume fraction.

For the NRB with notch radius R8, variations of the particle maximum principle stress, particle volume fraction and the matrix equivalent plastic strain are similar with NRB R4 in the early stage of tensile deformation. However, the reduction of the particle volume fraction at point E is much slower.

Fig.7 The evolution of mechanical parameters of NRB-R4

Fig.8 The evolution of mechanical parameters of NRB-R8

4.2 The evolution of void volume fraction

The void volume fraction represents the degree of matrix ductile damage. Fig. 9 shows the contours of volume fraction increments at tensile displacement of 0.174mm for NRB R4 and R8 respectively. The figures illustrate that the void growth rate for the NRB with smaller notch radius is higher at the middle section than that of the larger notch radius, since the higher stress triaxiality of the former promotes the voids growth.

Fig.9 The contour of volume fraction increment at $U_2=0.174\text{mm}$

The change of the void volume fraction increment with tensile deformation is shown in Fig.10. Due to the higher stress triaxiality, the volume fraction increment at point *C* is always higher than the one at point *E*.

Fig.10 The evolution of volume fraction nucleation at points *C* and *E*.

The void volume fraction is the sum of the void nucleation and void growth. The cracked particles are treated as the void nucleation. The void growth is closely related to the ductile damage of the matrix. Fig.11 shows the contour of void volume fraction at tensile displacement of 0.08mm. The void volume fraction is higher at the middle section of NRB specimens with smaller notch radius.

Fig.11 The contour of void volume fraction at $U_2=0.08\text{mm}$

Fig. 12 shows the curves of void volume fraction vs. tensile deformation at both points *C* and *E*. At the early stage of deformation, the evolution of void volume is mainly caused by the voids nucleation, which occurs earlier at edge point *E*. With the increase of deformation, the particle nucleation has come to an end and the material enters the intermediate deformation stage during which the void volume fraction increase steadily. Then, at the last stage of deformation, the void growth is boosted and the void coalescence results in the final fracture of the minimum section. At the intermediate and the last stage of deformation, the void volume fraction at point *C* is always larger than that of point *E*, which indicates that the micro cracks firstly arise at the very center of the specimens.

Fig.12 The evolution of volume fraction at points *C* and *E*.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In-situ $\text{TiB}_2/2024\text{Al}$ composites exhibits a mixed behaviour of ductile and brittle fractures. A ductile-brittle damage model is proposed according to the constitutive relations of every constituents and their fracture characteristics. Mori-Tanaka homogenization technique is adopted to describe stress and strain distributions among the TiB_2 particles and the Al matrix. The particles are isotropic, linear

elastic, brittle in nature and the strength is determined by the maximum principal stress criterion and subject to Weibull distribution. Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman (GTN) model is used to describe the plastic potential as well as the ductile fracture of the matrix. The proposed damage model is established with the uniaxial tension response and fracture of the smooth round bar and notched round bar specimens by the comparison between simulation and experiments. The simulation results of the notched round bar specimens reveal that the smaller notch radius corresponds to faster particle fracture, void nucleation and void growth, and smaller tensile deformation at fracture.

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